

COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF SOFTWARE DEFECT PREDICTION USING DATA MINING

**Rana Hammad Habib¹, Fazal Haq², Kalim ur Rehman³, Muhammad Usama Hafeez⁴,
Muhammad Ahmad⁵, Muhammad Hamza Afzal⁶, Muhammad Nabeel Afzal⁷**

¹Department of Computer Science, University of Central Punjab, Faisalabad, Pakistan,
prof.ranahammadhabib@gmail.com

²Department of Computer Science, Riphah International University, Faisalabad, Pakistan,
mrfazalhaq157@gmail.com

³Department of Computer Science, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan,
kaleem.ur.rehman@uaf.edu.pk

⁴Department of Computer Science, Riphah International University, Faisalabad, Pakistan,
usama176fsd@gmail.com

⁵Department of Computer Science, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan,
muhammadahmad4all@gmail.com

⁶Department of Computer Science, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan,
hamzaafzal67112@gmail.com

⁷Department of Computer Science, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan,
nabeelafzal361@gmail.com

Abstract

Software Defect Prediction is the area that is used to predict the defects before they occur. Now-a-days more reliable and accurate software's are produced for the users. Performance is compulsory for the software's and mostly depends upon the accuracy because software's should be worked accurately when they are delivered to end user. This means how much a software is best with respect to accuracy. In this research different algorithms are used to analyze the performance with respect to accuracy for the software defect prediction. The performance based accuracy of a software can be boosted up by predicting the faults. Hence the software fault prediction is utilized to produce very accurate and less costly new software's. For, this purpose classification based analysis is used in Weka to implement the data analysis. The data is collected from the open source and publically available data set like i.e promise data repository. In this paper the comparative comprehensive analysis are used and how these analysis shows the results regarding selecting the best algorithm for predicting the software faults.

1. Introduction

The globe business of software improvement appeared to be \$244 billion truly as specified the year 2010. Furthermore, to advisory information and firm technology, both demonstrate the importance of software in market and global general public sector round the world [11].

Software Defect Prediction (SDP) is the area of research that lies with building expectation models, which influence programming measurements to anticipate deformity inclined zones of a product.

Software developing is furnishing engineers with essential intends to institutionalize the improvement procedure and to build profitability. Be that as it may, shockingly the usage of a similar programming configuration may deliver programming frameworks with various quality, contingent upon how much the characterized forms connected and how experienced or inventive the venture group must average.

It is indefinable that to throw out the defects from the initial stages with respect to the software development life cycle and it is additionally considering that the cost of making and also modifying programming packages is typically shockingly high when inadequacies with respect to faults are generally distinguished from the later phases of the software development life cycle [12].

Determination and assurance with respect to presence of faults in software development life cycle stages is typically an essential procedure as it truly finds defective modules that are needed to refactoring and in addition to point by point evaluation [25]. In this way, much more mature software's are made and tested in order to produce high quality software. Software development expectation is truly a control in which figures deformity inclination with respect to long haul modules making utilization of vigorous prediction measurements furthermore celebrated imperfection of data. By method for mulling over computer software defects, expectation are frameworks, some kind of wander and could be sorted out more effectively, particularly evaluation furthermore support of stages [6].

A lot of difficulties occur while getting the defective data from the software developments and the major issue how and why to acquire the data from the repositories because of the lot of research involve in data acquisition. However simple method is to get the data from the NASA1 and as well as PROMISE2 data repositories [24]. Meanwhile the two data repositories are popular amongst researches and programmers. For the purpose of defect prediction Weka software is the most favorable and best choice amongst others. The data repositories PROMISE 2 and NASA 1 hosts many data sets. Computer scientist and researchers mainly and naively consideration in NASA Matric Data Program (MDP) for the data mining researches. In past the researchers have lot issues to acquire the data. Therefor early researchers used these data without any processing. There are websites the providing the facilities to download freely [16].

There are many techniques that are used for the software defect prediction but the classification is the technique that is discussed here and this technique is most powerful technique. The results of classification are normally used to find out how much the classification is best from one to others [22, 28]. Because there are too many classification techniques that are utilized but the way is that how to accomplished error free softwares. Therefore selecting the best technique for the software fault prediction result to reduce the chances of error in the software's [1].

Quality and reliability of the software is depend upon the error free software development. Classification is the technique that is used for the software defect prediction and also different types of algorithms are used.

Since the software defect prediction is useful for evaluating the software reliability and quality. Defect prediction comparatively shows the areas where defects may occur but it is also required the huge performance (classification) algorithm to predict the results. In the software defect

prediction there are classification models are produced and these models are very favorable in making the fault free software and they will be predicting the accurate observation for the making new software's. Basically classification models are used for predicting the latest perception about the shortcomings that may happen in the different software development phases [29].

This paper is organized in the following sections: in the second section there is descriptively represent the literature review. In the section 3, methodology is represented and in the section 4, result are represented and also make discussion on that results. In the section 5, conclusion is studied descriptively.

2. Related Work

Now a day most of models that are researched in order to find the defect. These models are used as the forecasting of errors that are occurred in the development of the software. There are too much damaged modules due to the improper classification in comparison to the inadequate modules. The significant level is measured of the classification method and characterized by using the algorithms [32]. It is inferred about the neural system the values of the defect that are produced in the neural system programing and also studied that how to improve the quality of the neural software. The result of this study was created a contrast between two strategies that they used in the research. The most prominent part of the defective areas are distinguished in this study and found the faulty modules [17].

It is proposed in a research that the defects are occur in every phase of the software development life cycle and scientist also researched with the help of other researchers, to find errors while developing the software. The errors are produced in the different zones of the modules. Researchers also found that the defects are occurs at the end every interim in the modules and every interim have the same length to the other interims. So, the classification method is the best approach to utilize here for fault prediction [8].

The software defect prediction is about three diverse fault prediction strategies. The researchers looked into and created a model by utilizing the C4.5, Naive Bayes, and 1R (Regression). They utilized the information set that is accessible on the NASA storehouse particularly the KC1 information set is most vital information they investigated in their reviews. They utilized each of the three defect prediction procedures on the KC1 information set and recommend comes about [21].

The examination in regard to software fault prediction by utilizing the data mining and diverse strategies will create ideal outcomes by utilizing C4.5. The researchers utilized the cumbersome information of Telco and connected distinctive software fault prediction strategies. In the examination the strategies that are utilized are based upon Support Vector Machine (SVM), C4.5, Logistic Regression (LR), and k-NN. At the end it is found that the best software fault prediction technique is a tree examination by utilizing the strategy of C4.5 [2].

The catal said that software production issue the forecast inquire about huge with all the PC programming issue finding before the happen and it in like manner having main problems tend to be consolidated into couple of zones, for instance, old investigation released going before season associated with at least 2013 the examination displayed all through recent years. He outlined 90

look into papers on programming disfigurement figure these papers were disperse from years 1990 to 2009 [6]. The researchers also scrutinized the effect associated with data set measuring, estimations sets and have accumulation methodologies with PC programming issue conjecture issues, which were in the past not minded this examination area [7].

The examination of such a large number of fault prediction methods is vital undertaking. It is proposed that the intelligibility and the execution while utilizing the product imperfection expectation is regularly relinquished or the other way around. The techniques that are utilized Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), k-NN, Multilayer perceptron's, Decision Tree, Bayesian conviction organize, Naive Bayes, Random Forest (RF), and RBF, strategies for the imperfection forecast. These all systems are utilized on the NASA information set and discover the outcomes about the best method [1].

There are used subgroup exposure related to the reasonable approach for predicting the deficiencies from the item. There are rules concerning known as incited rule that are used as a part of the estimate of deficiencies yet these guidelines are mined from the datasets. These fundamentals removed by using the relative estimation and after that these standards was associated with the new era for portrayal. Course of action is a real based methodology used to assemble the data and find the broken module or faulty code from the item. Classification is a factual based strategy used to classify the information and discover the deficient module or faulty code from the product. Though the software fault prediction classifiers are utilized for classification and these classifiers depend on the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) [27].

The utilization of two procedures as a part of the sort of programmer the predicted error factors from the item multifaceted nature estimations and especially machine learning count (DT, NB, BN, and LR with the effect of logarithmic change) and foresee the genuine site of the bugs that are known as the Maturing Related Bugs (MRB). These MRB was expect from the bewildering and sweeping programming's systems in light of the way that the broad structure are to a great degree mind boggling to find the issue from them [9, 20].

It is explained about the unwanted approaches that mustn't be established on insightful convenience, solitude in light of present circumstances of which unmistakable segments for example computational ability, straightforwardness besides especially understandability should moreover end up being in thought. Most of the item weakness desire they inquired about that the Logistic regression based examination and Random Forest (RF) examination are the best approach. It is also inferred that the software defect prediction should be done by using the above two approaches. Around the end of trial, they found the results against the NASA shroud dataset that is available publically to the all customers for programming inadequacy gauge. Toward the end of trial, they also found the outcomes against the NASA ECLIPSE dataset that is accessible publically to the all client for programming issue forecast [20].

In the research there are selected eight estimations out of 14 through an association examination using Spearman Rho. Among the metrics there were picked WMC and RFC, most extraordinary cyclomatic multifaceted nature and some size estimations. In addition, the amount of lines included or balanced ensuing to the past release was used. Undoubtedly, this change metric

was the best individual pointer of imperfections thickness and number of deficiencies. In the makers used fault and code measures data from the NASA Metric Data Program (MDP). There were 21 measures open as candidate pointers. Four interesting data sets were used, and the most indispensable estimations in each data set were picked using association based Confidence Factors (CFs). Dependent upon the data set used, the amount of factors was decreased from 21 to three to seven. Among the factors picked were McCabe's cyclomatic disperse quality and Halstead's astute number and inconvenience estimations. Moreover included were a couple line count estimations: the amount of lines including comments and number of clear lines [31].

The subset of the estimations which are associated with the work of Chidamber and Kemerer: WMC, DIT, RFC, NOC, CBO, LCOM. Their result exhibited that four estimations were tremendous in envisioning insufficiency slant: WMC, CBO, RFC and lines of code. DIT, NOC and to some degree LCOM, were not seen to be basic. In the system under review was a structure was written in C. Therefore, we consider the estimations inspected in this examination of less criticalness as our middle in this review is generally on thing organized structures. They in like manner fixated on the Halstead estimations suite and a decision of size estimations and the conjecture models yielded an exactness going from 0.73 to 0.87. The utilization of the estimations available through NASA MDP to take a gander at a couple data mining frameworks. The models yielded a precision of 0.83 to 0.93, and about most of the exactness and audit measures were over 0.9 [23].

The impact of a generous number of estimations on weakness slant; 28 coupling measures, 10 connection measures, 11 legacy related measures and 6 estimate measures. Each measure's impact on deficiency slant was surveyed through univariate strategic backslide. Three multivariate models were made; one using size estimations alone, one including object-masterminded measures like connection, coupling and legacy, and one including both the size measures and the thing arranged estimations as contender markers. The best model similarly as exactness and satisfaction were the model considering object-orchestrated estimations alone, i.e., without the size estimations. This model obtained 92% finish and 78% rightness using 10fold cross endorsement, instead of 94% satisfaction and 81% precision while assessing tolerability of-fit. The cross-endorsed precision of the model was 80% [5].

3. Classification

Classification is the way by which data mining is done. But for the defect prediction classification is the only choice that is better to predict the faulty modules from the softwares.

3.1 Classification Techniques

It is informed that the examination of a large number of fault prediction methods is vital undertaking. They propose that the intelligibility and the execution while utilizing the product imperfection expectation is regularly relinquished or the other way around. They utilized Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), k-NN, Multilayer perceptron's, Decision Tree, Bayesian conviction organize, Naive Bayes, Random Forest (RF), and RBF, strategies for the imperfection forecast. These all systems are utilized on the NASA information set and discover the outcomes about the best method [14].

It is expressed that now programming organizations are thinking about the nature of a product convey to the client. One of the significant issues that to quantify the nature of a product before given to the client they consider and researched the methods of Random Forest (RF), LMT, LDA, QDA, Logistic regression, Naive Bayes (NB), Bayes Net (BN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), k-NN, LARS, CART, C4.5, ADT and Multi-layer perceptron (MLP) acutely and expressively. It is found that every one of these systems are useful for programming fault prediction. They utilized Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to make correlation between these systems and to find what procedure is best one for fault prediction. At the subsequent of these methods they observed that Random Forest (RF) is the best procedure for the software defect prediction [18].

3.2 Data Set

There are many data sets that can be used for the software defect prediction but It is examined and use of the CK estimations on eight medium evaluated information organization systems in light of similar necessities used a couple outline estimations including McCabe's cyclomatic versatile quality on an Ericsson telecom structure used the CK estimations as a piece of conjunction with Briand's coupling estimations to anticipate inadequacies on a business Java system. CK estimations on a business C++/Java structure played out a near examination on Mozilla. Such a large number of frameworks are utilized for the blame expectation however the cyclomatic many-sided quality is most critical element that is anticipated from the given information set of NASA like KC1, KC2, KC3, PC1, PC2, PC3, and so on. Many programming dialects have distinctive cyclomatic unpredictability to include however this examination the correlation amongst C++ and Java and utilized the defects expectation measurements of CK and McCabe's [3, 10].

Software fault prediction is difficult errand while utilizing such a large number of systems the techniques like Random Forest (RF), Discriminant Analysis (DA), Decision Tree Algorithm (DTA), Regression Analysis (RA), classifiers and Several WEKA classifiers, it is hard to discover which strategy is best for software fault prediction. In spite of the fact that software fault prediction is mind boggling action so they utilized information set that is accessible publically [19]. They likewise differentiated Arbitrary Backwoods and 26 other showing methodology including calculated backslide and 20 procedures available through the WEKA gadget. The review contemplated the techniques using five differing datasets from the NASA MDP program, and despite the way that the results exhibited that Irregular Timberlands perform better than anything various other game plan frameworks with respect to precision and specificity, the results were not critical in four of the five data sets [15].

4. Proposed work

In the first step of methodology generally the scheme of frame work is learned and also learned about the algorithm that is used to calculate the accuracy for the future data. In this study each data set is composed of modules, number of defects and attributes. The modules of the software are characterized by the LOC (Line of Code). The data set is composed of the complexity metrics and these are taken from the McCabe metrics and Halstead complexity measures. In this research sixteen data sets are taken from the NASA MDP repository [4].

More over the data sets that are taken from developing the software by using the languages of the C, C++ and Java. The experimentation of this research is done by using the WEKA software tool. WEKA is the data mining software and especially used for data mining purpose and we will measure the accuracy of the algorithms by using this software by using the 10 fold cross validation [26, 30].

In the Fig 1 shows the example of the PC3 data set that is import in the weka and shows the defects present or not present.

Fig 1: PC3 Data set

In the Fig 2 shows the example of the work by using the NASA MDP data with 10 folds settings. This data set is comprises on PC3 dataset.

Fig 2: sample Output from Weka of PC3 Data set

We used 12 algorithms and 16 data set in this research to find out the accuracy of the best defect prediction algorithmic technique. This is because we want to calculate and analyze the best algorithm for the software defect prediction for improving the quality of the software.

In illustration the table 1 sows the summary of the data set with their characteristics. This dataset shows also the number of defects and to measure the performance of the on these data sets a confusion matrix is designed.

Data Set	Attribute	Modules	Defects
AR1	30	121	9
AR3	30	63	8
AR4	30	107	20
AR5	30	36	8
AR6	30	101	15
CM1	38	327	42
JM1	22	7782	1672
KC1	22	2109	326
KC2	22	522	107
KC3	40	194	36
MC1	39	1988	46
MC2	40	125	44
MW1	38	253	27
PC1	38	705	61

PC2	37	745	16
PC3	38	1077	134
PC4	38	1458	178
PC5	39	17186	516

Table 1: Data Set Characteristics

In the table 2 there is confusion matrix with respect to the positive and negative values are illustrated. The confusion matrix is based on the (TP, TN, FP, FN), now the performance with respect to accuracy is calculated by using this matrix.

Table 2: Confusion Matrix

Actual class	Positive	Negative
Positive	True Positive (TP)	False Negative (FN)
Negative	False Positive (FP)	True negative (TN)

- TP – Defect prone
- TN – Not Defect prone
- FN – Defect prone instance is incorrectly classified as not defect prone instance
- FP – An instance is classified as defect prone, but actually it is not

5. Results Evaluation

In the table 3 the performance of various algorithms are discussed in this research twelve algorithms are evaluated and find which one of the selected algorithm is best for the respective data type.

Accuracy is measured in order to find that how many percentage of predictions are correct [13]. It is also known as classification rate. Furthermore, accuracy is considered as the primary index in the software defect prediction. In this study we found that the Random Forest(RF) is best approach for predicting the data (AR4, AR6, MC1, MC2, PC1, PC5), ZeroR is best approach for predicting the data (AR1, CM1, MW1, PC2), LOG is best approach for predicting the data (JM1, KC1, PC4), Decision Tree(DT) is best approach for predicting the data (AR5, KC3), and Naïve Bayes, OneR and J48Graft are best approaches for predicting the data KC2, PC3 and AR3 respectively.

The accuracy of the algorithmic performance is measured by using the formula:

$$\text{Accuracy} = (TP + TN) / (TP+FP+FN+TN)$$

Methods	NB	LOG	DT	JRip	OneR	PART	ZEROR	J48	J48G	RF	RT	REPtree
AR1	85.12397	85.124	90.9091	90.9091	89.2562	90.9091	92.562	90.0826	90.0826	89.2562	89.2562	92.562
AR3	90.47619	82.5397	90.4762	90.4762	90.4762	88.8889	87.3016	87.3016	92.063	88.8889	87.3016	87.3016
AR4	84.11215	76.6355	82.243	85.047	83.1776	81.3084	81.3084	81.3084	82.243	85.047	77.5701	81.3084
AR5	83.33333	69.4444	86.111	77.7778	83.3333	83.3333	77.7778	83.3333	83.3333	80.5556	83.3333	77.7778
AR6	82.17822	76.2376	83.1683	85.1485	86.1386	80.198	85.1485	83.1683	84.1584	87.129	78.2178	82.1782
CM1	80.42813	84.0979	87.156	81.9572	85.0153	85.9327	87.156	83.792	83.1804	85.0153	79.5107	86.8502
JM1	78.19327	79.093	78.6687	78.7201	76.9082	78.5659	78.5145	76.4071	76.587	76.5484	70.9072	78.2961
KC1	82.36131	85.68	84.8743	84.5424	83.6415	84.8269	84.5424	84.5424	84.5899	85.4433	82.6932	85.1114
KC2	83.5249	82.9502	83.1418	82.1839	81.2261	82.1839	79.5019	81.4176	81.9923	82.1839	80.8429	81.6092
KC3	78.86598	77.8351	82.99	81.4433	76.2887	77.8351	81.4433	79.3814	80.9278	78.3505	70.6186	79.3814
MC1	88.8833	97.3843	97.334	97.2334	97.4849	97.1328	97.6861	97.3843	97.6538	97.837	97.0825	97.6861
MC2	72	61.6	68.8	69.6	64.8	66.4	64.8	71.2	71.2	72	64	68
MW1	81.42292	86.9565	88.1423	88.9328	86.166	84.1897	89.328	86.9565	87.3518	86.166	85.3755	88.5375
PC1	88.08511	91.4894	90.2128	91.6312	91.0638	88.6525	91.3475	90.0709	90.0709	92.057	89.7872	90.0709
PC2	90.73826	96.6443	97.852	97.7181	97.5839	97.3154	97.852	97.1812	97.7181	97.3154	95.5705	97.852
PC3	35.6546	87.0938	86.1653	86.6295	88.022	86.6295	87.558	84.9582	85.5153	85.5153	83.2869	87.0009
PC4	87.03704	91.564	89.2318	88.2716	89.4376	89.3004	87.7915	88.1344	88.4774	91.0151	87.5857	88.1344
PC5	96.41569	97.2769	97.2827	97.3118	96.8055	97.3641	96.9976	97.4631	97.5096	97.545	97.1605	97.4631

6. Conclusion

Defects occur during the software development and maintenance but in any case when defects occur there might be the poor quality of the software recorded. Therefore, when the defects occur software failure cases will report. Since the software defect prediction deals with the quality of the software because if the defects are predicted before they occur in the software so it will lead the huge quality of the software.

The data mining's best techniques are used to predict and analyze the software defects from the huge number of data set in order to improve the quality and efficiency of the software. In this research work it has been concluded that the Random Forest is the comprehensive technique that is used to predict the defects at the high accuracy percentage where as other techniques are relatively lower accuracy rate as compare to Random Forest. So for the defect prediction Random Forest is the best choice.

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